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FENG 498 PROJECT REPORT

Analysis of the effects of uncertainties in the ephemerides and gravitational fields of Phobos in the execution of very low altitude flybys by a solar sail-propelled SmallSat orbiting Mars

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Abstract

We live in an exhilarating period when humanity's exploration of the cosmos is accelerating. To this end, we propose a solar sail flyby mission to Phobos, as it is one of the most intriguing places to visit in our solar system due to its unique morphology. Accurate navigation for such a mission requires precise gravitational models. This study presents a methodology for describing the gravitational field of any object using spherical harmonics. We present a numerical way of calculating the coefficients for the spherical harmonics representation from the discretized shape model. By using two different shape models for Phobos, we reproduce the established homogeneous gravitational field in the existing literature for Phobos. Afterwards, based on the existing literature, a possible interior structure is determined. Second-order Stokes' coefficients of this heterogeneous Phobos closely match the ones provided in Yang et al. (2019) [2]. Lastly, we compare the gravitational force of Phobos to the solar radiation force around Mars to highlight the importance of gravitational uncertainties for this mission.

List of Symbols

NumPy NumPy is an open-source Python library that provides support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a collection of mathematical functions to operate on these arrays. It forms the foundation of the scientific computing ecosystem in Python [3].

PyVista PyVista: Open-source Python library for 3D visualization and mesh analysis. Built on VTK, it supports scientific computing, spatial datasets, and interactive plotting [4].

Matplotlib Matplotlib is an open-source Python library for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations. It provides an interface for generating plots, histograms, bar charts, and other graphical representations of data [5].

Mpmath A Python library for arbitrary-precision floating-point arithmetic. It supports real and complex numbers, matrices, and special functions, making it useful for numerical and symbolic computation with high precision [6].

Pymeshfix A Python wrapper for MeshFix, a tool used to automatically repair 3D triangle meshes. It removes holes, fills gaps, and corrects non-manifold edges, producing watertight and manifold meshes suitable for voxelization or format conversion [7].

SBMT SBMT (Small Body Mapping Tool) is a NASA-developed software that enables the mapping, analysis, and visualization of small celestial bodies. It aids researchers in processing and interpreting data from asteroids, comets, and similar objects, offering valuable insights into their shape, structure, and composition [8].

η The reflectivity efficiency of the solar sail, defined as the fraction of incident solar radiation that is effectively reflected..

r radius to a given particle.

ϕ Latitude.

λ Longitude.

R Maximum radius possible in the body.

GM Gravitational Parameter: the product of the gravitational constant (G) and the mass of the body (M).

Brillouin sphere The smallest sphere that completely encloses a physical body.

Sympy Python library for symbolic mathematics [9].

Center of Mass (CoM) The point at which an object's mass can be considered to be concentrated, calculated as the weighted average position of its mass distribution. For homogeneous bodies, it coincides with the geometric center.

Center of Figure (CoF) The geometric center of an object's figure, defined as the arithmetic mean position of all points on the object (assuming uniform density).

NASA-GMAT NASA-GMAT (General Mission Analysis Tool) is an open-source software developed by NASA for mission design and analysis. It provides tools for trajectory optimization, spacecraft operations, and mission planning, making it a key resource for engineers and researchers in the aerospace community [23].

$C_{\ell m}$ the spherical-harmonic cosine coefficient.

$S_{\ell m}$ the spherical-harmonic sine coefficient.

$P_{\ell m}$ Associated Legendre Polynomial.

stereophotoclinometry Stereophotoclinometry (SPC) is a technique to extract topographic information from images acquired by spacecraft.

QSO A quasi-satellite orbit is a configuration where a smaller body shares nearly the same orbital period as a larger one around a central attractor, giving the appearance of a long-term companion without being gravitationally bound like a true satellite.

1 Introduction

The Martian moon Phobos has drawn significant interest from the scientific community due to its peculiar orbit around Mars and its unique morphology [10]. A mission to this moon could reveal insights into its origin and deepen our understanding of the solar system. In 2026, JAXA will launch the first mission to collect surface samples from Phobos and return them to Earth [11]. However, current knowledge about this moon remains limited. For missions close to irregularly shaped bodies like Phobos, gravitational forces become significant perturbations. This study aims to analyze uncertainties in Phobos' gravitational field specifically for a solar sail flyby mission and to produce a realistic gravity file for use in [NASA-GMAT](#). Initially, two different shape models will be developed for use in [PyVista](#). These models will then be voxelized and divided into regions. These cells will be used to produce realistic Stokes' coefficients that match the current best estimation. Lastly, the produced gravitational field will be compared to solar radiation pressure to demonstrate its significance in the context of the mission. This entire project will use Python to simulate and produce data. All Python scripts will be provided as supplementary material.

1.1 Problem Statement

Most objects in our solar system are highly irregularly shaped [12]. Their irregular shapes cause irregular gravitational fields. In the case of Phobos, its irregular shape and extremely perturbed environment present additional challenges [10]. Given the mission duration, accurate gravitational field models of Mars and Phobos are critical. However, current knowledge of Phobos is limited. To address this, we will combine existing flyby data with interior-structure predictions to produce a reliable Phobos gravity field for NASA-GMAT simulations. By using a solar sail, we eliminate chemical-propulsion carbon emissions and reduce launch mass, while solar energy provides effectively unlimited fuel. Finally, a controlled deorbiting at the end of the mission prevents space debris. This approach sets a sustainable benchmark for space exploration, directly supporting SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

1.2 Motivation

Phobos is one of the most exotic places in the solar system. It can shed light on the earlier days of the solar system. A mission around and on Phobos would allow us to determine its gravitational field [13]. This would help us better understand its interior structure and therefore its origins. Consequently, it is of utmost importance to have the best possible estimation of its gravitational field for a mission around Phobos. Additionally, the mission tests the capabilities of a solar sail in a highly perturbed environment, possibly making it an attractive choice for missions to other celestial bodies in the solar system.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Willner et al. (2014), *Phobos' shape and topography models*

Willner et al. (2014) [14] combine the High-Resolution Stereo Camera (HRSC) aboard Mars Express and Viking Orbiter stereo-photogrammetry to produce a global digital terrain model at 100 m/pixel and a spherical-harmonic expansion to degree and order 45, which they provide in the appendix. Given the accuracy of this model, it will be used to reconstruct Phobos's shape, from which the gravitational potential will be computed via the method provided in [15] and references therein. According to the shape's spherical harmonics model, they calculate Phobos's volume to be 5741.5 km^3 ($\pm 0.6\%$), bulk density to be $1.860 \pm 0.013 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, and principal moments of inertia to be $A=0.3605$, $B=0.4267$, and $C=0.4998$, resulting in a forced libration amplitude of 1.14° under a homogeneous-mass assumption. They improve the triaxial ellipsoid dimensions of Phobos to $13.03 \times 11.40 \times 9.14 \text{ km}$. Lastly, the study presents dynamic height ($\pm 800 \text{ m}$ variations) and slope (up to 40.6°) maps for Phobos.

2.2 Le Maistre et al. (2019), *Signature of Phobos' interior structure in its gravity field and libration*

Le Maistre et al. (2019) [15] study how Phobos's interior affects its gravity field and libration amplitude. They start from the shape model of Willner (2014) [14] and divide

it into 500 m cubes of rock, void, and ice. Next, they provide a numerical method from existing literature to calculate the spherical harmonics coefficients, which will be implemented in this study. The study considers 6 different scenarios: a random “rubble pile,” a “heavily fractured” zone under Stickney, a “porous compressed” core beneath the crater, and two ice-rich variants. Each scenario is constrained to match Phobos’s bulk mass and external shape. For each model, they derive moments of inertia, forced libration amplitude, low-degree gravity coefficients C_{20}, C_{22} , and **Center of Mass (CoM)** vs. **Center of Figure (CoF)** offsets. They find that only the fractured and compressed models produce large ($> 5\%$) deviations in libration and $10\sim 30\%$ shifts in C_{20}, C_{22} . They exclude the heavily fractured case because its libration amplitude does not match observations. This leaves the porous-compressed scenario as the only one consistent with all geodetic data. It suggests a globally porous Phobos with localized compaction beneath Stickney. This scenario will be considered to model the most realistic interior for Phobos.

2.3 Yang et al. (2019), *The second-degree gravity coefficients of Phobos*

Building on GM and harmonic estimates by [16] and [17], Yang et al. (2019) [2] used a regularized inverse technique to two-way Doppler data from the 2010 and 2013 Mars Express Phobos flybys to calculate the second order spherical harmonics coefficients. These coefficients were compared to the constant-density forward model of [18] to assess interior heterogeneity. They obtained

$$GM = (7.0765 \pm 0.0075) \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}, \quad C_{20} = -0.1378 \pm 0.0348, \quad C_{22} = 0.0166 \pm 0.0153.$$

with the significantly lower C_{20} (vs. the homogeneous-shape value) implying equatorial mass concentration. This analysis will be considered for the interior modeling of Phobos.

2.4 Scheeres et al. (2019), *Dynamics in the Phobos environment*

Scheeres et al. (2019) [10] use an exact polyhedral gravity model to investigate spacecraft dynamics in the highly perturbed environment around Phobos. Their analysis considers the moon’s irregular shape, the strong tidal forces from Mars, and Phobos’s orbital eccentricity, all of which significantly affect nearby trajectories. They map surface accelerations and slopes. The study derives speed limits for surface motion and identifies regions where material can escape through L_1/L_2 necks. They also analyze the hovering motion about Phobos, and state that almost all hovering locations will be unstable. In this study, the analysis provided by Scheeres et al.(2019) [10] will remain at a more introductory level due to the nature of a flyby mission.

2.5 Guo et al. (2021): *Lighter Core For Phobos?*

Guo et al. (2021) [19] explore the possible density configurations for Phobos by looking at the previously published second-degree gravity coefficients C_{20} and C_{22} from the study by Yang et al. (2019) [2]. By implementing a simple two-layer core-mantle model to shape model produced by Willner et el. (2014) [14] in which they vary core size and density under the constraint of Phobos’s known mass and volume, they study the density characteristics of the core and the mantle. By exploring both a denser-core and a lighter-core scenario, they demonstrate that the current estimates of the C_{20} from observations suggest a mantle-denser (i.e., core lighter than mantle) configuration. This “lighter-core” result supports hypotheses of material migration toward the surface whether driven by rapid rotation in a rubble-pile structure (as has been suggested for Bennu) or by a staged (hot-then-cold) accretion process. The lighter-core model will be implemented in this study.

2.6 Ernst et al. (2023), *High-resolution shape models of Phobos and Deimos from stereophotoclinometry*

Ernst et al. (2023) [20] generated high-resolution shape models of Mars’ moons Phobos and Deimos using [stereophotoclinometry](#). Phobos’ ellipsoid axes were refined to $12.95 \pm 0.04 \times 11.30 \pm 0.04 \times 9.16 \pm 0.03$ km volume (5695 ± 32 km³), while Deimos’ model ($8.04 \pm 0.08 \times 5.89 \pm 0.06 \times 5.11 \pm 0.05$ km, volume (1033 ± 19 km³) revealed its

first geological structures. They compare their shape models with the previous models. They derive gravitational acceleration and slope maps for the shapes that were developed. Datasets were archived in NASA PDS and the [SBMT](#), enabling mission planning (e.g., JAXA’s MMX) and geophysical studies.

2.7 Yamamoto et al. (2024), *Simulation of gravity field estimation of Phobos for Martian Moon eXploration (MMX)*

Yamamoto et al. (2024) [13] simulate MMX spacecraft quasi-satellite orbits (2D and 3D QSOs) and an ascending ballistic trajectory to assess gravity field recovery via Doppler, LIDAR range, and image landmark data. They show that degree-2 Stokes coefficients C_{20} , C_{22} can be retrieved to $\sim 0.1\%$ accuracy from two-dimensional QSOs, while low-altitude 3D-QSO observations might detect the coefficients to degree and order 5, sufficient to detect regional density anomalies beneath Stickney. Furthermore, ascending-trajectory LIDAR data allow local density structure parameters (layer boundary or density) to be estimated to be better than 0.2% , demonstrating MMX’s capability to resolve both global and local Phobos interior heterogeneity.

3 Methodology

3.1 Gravitational Models

There are a few ways to model a gravitational field of an irregularly shaped object [12, 21]. Depending on the nature of the mission, one must select an appropriate model such as the spherical harmonics approach and the ellipsoidal harmonics approach [12, 21]. Spherical harmonics are commonly employed for gravitational field modeling in missions operating at sufficiently high altitudes [22]. Additionally, [NASA-GMAT](#) uses spherical harmonics modeling to represent the gravitational field of celestial bodies [23].

With reference to [24, 12, 21], the spherical harmonics representation of the gravity potential is given as follows;

$$U(r, \lambda, \phi) = -\frac{GM}{r} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^{\ell} \sum_{m=0}^{\ell} [C_{\ell m} \cos(m\lambda) + S_{\ell m} \sin(m\lambda)] P_{\ell m}(\sin \phi), \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Visualization of **Brillouin sphere** expansion around an irregular object, along with r and R vectors.

As seen in (Fig.1), r represents the position vector of any particle outside the **Brillouin sphere**, while R represents the maximum possible radius within the body. $C_{\ell m}$ and $S_{\ell m}$ are the Stokes' coefficients. They are derived based on observations coming from spacecraft data [21]. The downside of this model is that inside the **Brillouin sphere**, the solution becomes unstable [21, 12]. This makes the model a poor choice for missions very close to the surface of an irregularly shaped body [12]. However, due to the nature of a flyby mission, this model remains a valid and reliable way to represent the gravitational field of a body.

3.1.1 Mapping the gravitational field

In order to visualize and model the gravitational fields with spherical harmonics, the Python library `Sympy` was chosen.

The Stokes' coefficients and $P_{\ell m}$ are normalized to make the computations more efficient. For further information, we refer the reader to the references [24, 15, 21]. It is important to understand that this modeling with `Sympy` comes with its limitations, mainly after the 50th degree, the terms become too large for `Sympy` to handle and the code gives an error. Fortunately, this mission requires much less accuracy in the gravitational field.

To test the validity of the `Sympy`-based implementation, the Martian gravity map from JPL Horizons [25] with the one generated by this study were compared. Figure 2 plots, in the top panel, the JPL-computed acceleration anomalies (degrees ≥ 2), and in the bottom panel the corresponding gravitational acceleration map generated in this study. To produce the gravitational map, the gradient of the scalar potential function was taken in Python with `Sympy`. This expression was then turned into `NumPy` function to be used in computations.

```
1 import sympy as sp
2 def kronecker(m):
3     if m == 0:
4         return 1
5     else:
6         return 0
7
8 lam , phi, r = sp.symbols("lam phi r")
9
10 # Lam represents the longitude
11 # Phi represents the latitude
12
13 u = 0
14 degree = 4
15 for n in range(0, degree+1):
16     for m in range(0, n+1):
17         nn = coeff_list[(n,m)][0]
18         mm = coeff_list[(n,m)][1]
19
```

```

20     Nnm =
        sp.sqrt((2-kronecker(m))*(2*n+1)*sp.factorial(n-m)/sp.factorial(n+m)).eval
21
22     R_nm = sp.assoc_legendre(n,m,sp.sin(phi))*Nnm*sp.cos(m*lam)
23     S_nm = sp.assoc_legendre(n,m,sp.sin(phi))*Nnm*sp.sin(m*lam)
24
25     u += (r_phobos/r)**n * (nn*R_nm +mm*S_nm)
26
27 u = u*k_phobos/r
28
29 a_r = sp.diff(u,r)
30 a_lam = sp.cancel(sp.diff(u,lam)/(r*sp.cos(phi)))
31 a_phi = sp.cancel(sp.diff(u,phi)/r)
32 a = sp.sqrt(a_r**2+a_phi**2+a_lam**2)

```

Listing 1: Taking the gradient of a scalar potential function in spherical coordinates in Python with [SymPy](#)

```

1  import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
2  import numpy as np
3  num_points = 200
4  long_vals = np.linspace(0, 2*np.pi, num_points) # Longitude
5  lat_vals = np.linspace(-np.pi / 2+np.deg2rad(3), np.pi /
        2-np.deg2rad(3), num_points) # Latitude
6  Long, Lat = np.meshgrid(long_vals, lat_vals)
7  a_func = sp.lambdify((lam, phi,r), a, "numpy")
8  a_vals = a_func(Long, Lat,3400e3)
9  a_vals = np.array(a_vals, dtype=float)
10 a_vals = (a_vals - k_mars/(3400e3**2))*1e5 # Turning it to mGal
11
12 plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
13 plt.contourf(Long * 180 / np.pi, Lat * 180 / np.pi, a_vals,
        levels=500, cmap="turbo")
14 plt.colorbar(label=r"Gravitational Potential (mGal)")
15 plt.xlabel("Longitude")
16 plt.ylabel("Latitude")
17 plt.savefig(f"Mars-{degree}x{degree}-gravity.png",dpi=1000)
18 plt.show()

```

Listing 2: Taking the gradient of a scalar potential function in spherical coordinates in Python with [Matplotlib](#)

Figure 2: The Martian gravitational field map for second order and higher terms provided by JPL Horizons [25] and this study.

By taking a closer look at the code in 2, one will notice that the latitude coverage is incomplete. The polar regions were excluded from the calculation to avoid division by 0, as shown in equation 2. However, this does not affect the calculation in the following sections regarding the maximum force exerted by Phobos' gravitational field, as the maximum potential lies in the equatorial region. Lastly, we subtracted the point-mass

acceleration from the overall acceleration to obtain an acceleration map of Mars that captures contributions from second-order and higher terms. For further details, see Section A.

$$\mathbf{a} = -\vec{\nabla}U(r, \lambda, \phi) = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial r} \hat{u}_r - \frac{\partial U}{\partial \phi} \frac{1}{r} \hat{u}_\phi - \frac{\partial U}{\partial \lambda} \frac{1}{r \cos \phi} \hat{u}_\lambda \quad (2)$$

3.2 Shape Models

Given the uncertainties in the flyby data around Phobos, estimating Phobos' gravitational field necessitates two critical components: an accurate shape model and a physically plausible density distribution. The workflow is:

It is clear that the accuracy of the shape model is crucial. Small errors in the shape model can propagate into the density estimation and, ultimately, the spherical harmonics. Thus, our study will use the shape models by Willner et al. (2014) [14] and Ernst et al. (2023) [20] to mitigate the error related with each shape. While the shape model by Ernst et al. (2023) is available in [SBMT](#), the shape model of Willner et al. (2014) [14] is not available in [SBMT](#). Fortunately, the study provides the spherical harmonics coefficients up until degree and order 45 for the shape model. Thus, we were able to produce the model with the Python libraries [PyVista](#) and [SymPy](#). The following radius equation in spherical coordinates is provided in following references [15, 10].

$$\rho(\phi, \lambda) = \sum_{j=0}^J \sum_{k=0}^j \left[A_{jk} \cdot \cos(k\lambda) + B_{jk} \cdot \sin(k\lambda) \right] \cdot P_{jk}(\sin \phi) \quad (3)$$

This equation was then modeled in Python with [SymPy](#). The resulting shape of Phobos was turned into a `.obj` file with [PyVista](#).

3.2.1 Modeling and Producing the Shape of Phobos in Python

As the first step, the Stokes' coefficients provided by [14] were saved into a dictionary with its keys being a tuple of (n,m) meanwhile the values as a list $[C_{\ell m}, S_{\ell m}]$.

```
1 | coeff_list = {}
```

```

2 with open("TABLEA2.dat", "r") as f:
3     for line in f:
4         line = line.strip().split()
5
6         n = line[0]
7         m = line[1]
8         Anm = line[2]
9         Bnm = line[4]
10
11        n = int(n)
12        m = int(m)
13        Anm = float(Anm)
14        Bnm = float(Bnm)
15        coeff_list[(n,m)] = [Anm,Bnm]

```

Listing 3: Saving the coefficients into a dictionary

After obtaining the coefficients, the equation 3 was modeled with **Sympy** to the order and degree of 45.

```

1 import sympy as sp
2 lam , phi = sp.symbols("lam phi")
3 # Lam represents the longitutude of Phobos
4 # Phi represents the latitude of Phobos
5 r = 0
6 for n in range(0,46):
7     for m in range(0,n+1):
8         print(n,m)
9
10        r += (coeff_list[(n,m)][0]*sp.cos(m*lam) +
              coeff_list[(n,m)][1]*sp.sin(m*lam))*sp.assoc_legendre(n,m,sp.sin(phi))

```

Listing 4: Equation 3 with Sympy

The radius vector as a function of λ and ϕ was turned from a symbolic expression in **Sympy** into a **NumPy** function with the help of `.lambdify()` function.

```

1 R_func = sp.lambdify((lam, phi), r, "numpy")
2 num_points = 400
3 long_vals = np.linspace(-np.pi, np.pi, num_points)
4 lat_vals = np.linspace(-np.pi/2, np.pi/2, num_points)

```

```

5 Long, Lat = np.meshgrid(long_vals, lat_vals)
6 R_vals = R_func(Long, Lat)
7 R_vals = np.array(R_vals, dtype=float)
8 Long = np.array(Long, dtype=float)
9 Lat = np.array(Lat, dtype=float)
10 X = R_vals * np.cos(Lat) * np.cos(Long)
11 Y = R_vals * np.cos(Lat) * np.sin(Long)
12 Z = R_vals * np.sin(Lat)
13
14 import pyvista as pv
15
16 grid = pv.StructuredGrid(X,Y,Z)
17 plotter = pv.Plotter()
18 plotter.add_mesh(grid)
19 plotter.export_obj(f"phobos-willner14-{num_points}.obj")
20 plotter.show()

```

Listing 5: Turning the radius equation into a NumPy function and saving the result as an .obj file.

3.2.2 Using the shape model of Ernst et al. (2023) in PyVista

In the SBMT, by following the steps provided in Figure 3 and Figure 4, the shape file can be exported as .obj file at a resolution of your choosing. For this particular case, the resolution of Phobos was selected as very high, which might take a few minutes to load in SBMT depending on the quality of your hardware.

Figure 3: Selection of Phobos in SBMT

Figure 4: Exporting the shape of Phobos in SBMT

Next, the shape file could easily be imported in Python with the help of [PyVista](#) to be used for gravitational calculation as described in [Section 3.3](#).

```
1 import pyvista as pv
2 mesh = pv.read("phobos-shape-very-high.obj")
3 mesh["Radial Distance (km)"] = np.array(mesh.points)
4 plotter = pv.Plotter()
5 plotter.add_mesh(
6     mesh,
7     scalars="Radial Distance (km)",
8     cmap="turbo",
9     scalar_bar_args=dict(
10         vertical=True,
11         position_x=0.85,
12         position_y=0.3,
13         width=0.1,
14         height=0.5
15     )
16 )
17
18 plotter.isometric_view()
19 plotter.save_graphic('ernst-shape.pdf')
20 plotter.show()
```

Listing 6: Exporting the `.obj` shape file in Python with [PyVista](#)

Due to the method used to generate the shape, compatibility issues may arise when attempting to convert the `.obj` file into formats such as `.3ds`, or during voxelization. Thus, to fix the errors in the produced shape, [Pymeshfix](#) library was used. The code is provided in [H](#).

3.2.3 Comparison of the Shape Models of Willner et al. (2014) and Ernst et al. (2023)

The computed shape of Phobos in [Section 3.2.1](#) has a volume of 5741.0614 km^3 and an average radius of 10.5 km. While the calculated volume matches the values provided in Willner et al. (2014) [[14](#)] and Le Maistre (2019) [[15](#)], the average radius deviates by a few percent. This discrepancy in the radius might be due to the method used to produce

the shape, as a higher density of points in the polar regions, where the radius is smaller, lowers the overall average. The resulting shape is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The produced shape of Phobos from Willner et al. (2014)

Figure 6: The Phobos shape taken from SBMT

By directly exporting the shape model of Ernst et al. (2023) from SBMT as .obj file, the following shape model is obtained as shown in Figure 6. The exported shape has a volume of 5695.052 km^3 and an average radius of 11.0977 km , which is consistent with the stated values in Ernst et al. (2023) [20].

As a final addition to this section, a comparison of the radius vectors for each shape revealed that the largest radius difference was 689.18 meters, while the average radius difference was calculated to be 208.4 meters.

Figure 7: Difference between the two shapes in meters viewed on the xy plane

Figure 8: Difference between the two shapes in meters viewed on the xz plane

3.3 Discretization and Computation of Spherical Harmonics Coefficients of An Object

The gravitational field of an object is a direct result of the mass distribution within the body [21]. With an accurate model of this distribution, a reliable representation of the object's gravitational field can be obtained. The methodology provided in [15] and references therein provides a way to calculate the spherical harmonics of any discretized shape. By calculating the coefficients for each individual cube, the spherical harmonics coefficients of the whole body could be determined. The coefficients of each cube are calculated in the following way;

$$\text{for } l = 0 : \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{0,0}^i \\ \bar{S}_{0,0}^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{for } l = 1 : \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{1,1}^i \\ \bar{S}_{1,1}^i \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \begin{bmatrix} x_i/R \\ y_i/R \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{for } l > 1 : \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{l,l}^i \\ \bar{S}_{l,l}^i \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2l-1}{\sqrt{2l(2l+1)}} \begin{bmatrix} x_i/R & -y_i/R \\ y_i/R & x_i/R \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{l-1,l-1}^i \\ \bar{S}_{l-1,l-1}^i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Subdiagonal } (m = l - 1) : \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{l,l-1}^i \\ \bar{S}_{l,l-1}^i \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2l-1}{\sqrt{2l+1}} \frac{z_i}{R} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{l-1,l-1}^i \\ \bar{S}_{l-1,l-1}^i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Vertical (fixed } m) : \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{l,m}^i \\ \bar{S}_{l,m}^i \end{bmatrix} = (2l-1) \sqrt{\frac{2l-1}{(2l+1)(l+m)(l-m)}} \frac{z_i}{R} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{l-1,m}^i \\ \bar{S}_{l-1,m}^i \end{bmatrix} \\ - \sqrt{\frac{(2l-3)(l+m-1)(l-m-1)}{(2l+1)(l+m)(l-m)}} \left(\frac{r_i}{R}\right)^2 \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{l-2,m}^i \\ \bar{S}_{l-2,m}^i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Figure 9: The scheme of the equations 4, 5, 6 for the i^{th} cube

Figure 10: The scheme of the equation 7 for the i^{th} cube

Figure 11: The scheme of the equation 8 for the i^{th} cube

After calculating the coefficients for each cube, the coefficients of the entire body can be calculated.

$$M\bar{C}_{l,m} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{tot}}} d^3 \rho_i \bar{C}_{l,m}^i, \quad (9)$$

$$M\bar{S}_{l,m} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{tot}}} d^3 \rho_i \bar{S}_{l,m}^i. \quad (10)$$

where;

M is the total mass of the body,

d is the side length of each cube,

ρ_i is the density of the i^{th} cube,

$\bar{C}_{l,m}^i, \bar{S}_{l,m}^i$ are the degree–order coefficients of the i^{th} cube,

N_{tot} is the total number of cubes.

3.4 Discretization of Phobos in PyVista

After exporting the `.obj` file as shown in 6, the mesh can be discretized with the help of `.voxelize()` function. Depending on the accuracy desired, one can assign a density value to control the size of the cubes used to represent the mesh when calling the function. Depending on the units used in the mesh (e.g. SBMT shapes are in kilometers), one can adjust the size of the cubes used in for mesh. However, the smaller the size the slower the computation. Therefore, 500 m or 0.5 km was used for the computations in this study.

```

1 import pyvista as pv
2 density = 0.5
3 # The obj. is kms. Thus, the side length of each cube ( density ) is
  given in km.
4 # For the shape produced by the coefficients provided by Willner et
  al. (2014), the units are in meters.
```

```

5 mesh = pv.read("phobos-shape-very-high.obj")
6 mesh = pv.voxelize(mesh,density=density)

```

Listing 7: Voxelizing the .obj shape file in Python with [PyVista](#)

Figure 12: Voxelized shape of Phobos (300m)

Figure 13: Voxelized shape of Phobos (500m)

3.4.1 Selection of particular regions and accessing the corresponding cubes in [PyVista](#)

As described in Section 3.3, upon discretizing the shape, one can calculate the Stokes' coefficients of the entire body under the assumption that the position of each cube can be used in the calculations. Fortunately, the `.get_cell()` function in [PyVista](#) allows us to get the i^{th} cube and its properties.

```

1 import pyvista as pv
2 import mpmath
3
4 # https://docs.pyvista.org/api/core/_autosummary/pyvista.cell
5 for i in range(mesh.n_cells):
6     cell_mesh = mesh.get_cell(i)
7     x= mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[0])
8     y= mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[1])
9     z =mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[2])

```

Listing 8: Continuing from 7, the center of each cell is obtained with respect to the [Center of Figure \(CoF\)](#)

To select a particular region, the `.clip_box()` function in [PyVista](#) was preferred in this study. Alternatively, `.threshold` function could have been used to isolate sub-surface areas as done by Guo et. al (2021) [19]. However, `.clip_box()` function provides more flexibility in selecting regions.

```

1  # Selecting regions within Ernst et al. (2023)
2  # (x_min, x_max, y_min, y_max, z_min, z_max)
3  bounds = (2, 30, -30,-2, -5, 5) # Stickney! ----> here, pay
   attention to the units!
4  bounds1 = (-x_eq_bound, 2-(density+0.001), -y_eq_bound,y_eq_bound,
   -z_bound, z_bound) # center
5  bounds11 = (-x_eq_bound, 2-(density+0.001),
   y_eq_bound+(density+0.001),30, -z_bound, z_bound) # center edge1
6  bounds12 = (-x_eq_bound, 2-(density+0.001),
   -30,-y_eq_bound-(density+0.001), -z_bound, z_bound) #center edge2
7  bound_edge1 =(-30, -x_eq_bound-(density+0.001), -30,30, -z_bound,
   z_bound) #edge 1
8  bound_edge2 = (2, 30, -2+(density+0.001),30, -z_bound, z_bound) #edge
   2
9
10 extracted = mesh.clip_box(bounds,
   invert=False,progress_bar=True,crinkle=True) # Stickney
11 extracted1 = mesh.clip_box(bounds1,
   invert=False,progress_bar=True,crinkle=True) # Center
12
13 # Edges of Phobos
14 extracted2 = mesh.clip_box(bound_edge1,
   invert=False,progress_bar=True,crinkle=True)
15 extracted2 = extracted2.merge(mesh.clip_box(bound_edge2,
   invert=False,progress_bar=True,crinkle=True))
16 # Center Edges
17 extracted3 = mesh.clip_box(bounds11,
   invert=False,progress_bar=True,crinkle=True)
18 extracted3 = extracted3.merge(mesh.clip_box(bounds12,
   invert=False,progress_bar=True,crinkle=True))

```

Listing 9: Selecting regions within Ernst et al. (2023) Phobos model that will be assigned different density values

Figure 14: Selected Regions viewed from xz plane

Figure 15: Selected Regions viewed from xy plane

The shape of Phobos was divided into 5 regions based on the possible assumptions made in Section 2 about the interior. In the code, to prevent boundary overlaps, one boundary was offset by the length of a cell's side. Figure 16,17 illustrate a scenario where boundaries intersect. When assigning density values to these regions, possible overlap could cause density distribution errors.

Figure 16: Case illustrating the overlap in xy plane

Figure 17: Case illustrating the overlap in xz plane

3.4.2 Density Allocation and Distribution

Upon selecting the appropriate regions, the density allocations could be assigned to each cell. By using the methodology of Le Maistre et al. (2019) [15], each cell is assigned

one of three density values. In this study, porous cells are given a density of 0 kg/m^3 , icy cells are assigned 940 kg/m^3 , and the density of rock cells is calculated based on the overall mass balance of Phobos. In particular, if M is the total mass, d is the side length of each cube, ρ_{ice} is the density of ice, N_{ice} is the number of icy cells, and N_{rock} is the number of rock cells, then the rock density is computed as;

$$\rho_{\text{rock}} = \frac{M - \rho_{\text{ice}}d^3N_{\text{ice}}}{d^3N_{\text{rock}}} \quad (11)$$

```

1 import mpmath
2 rho =
   [mpmath.mpmathify("0"), mpmath.mpmathify("940e9"), mpmath.mpmathify("0")]
   #kg/km3 (Ernst 2023)
3
4 percentage_porous = float(input("What percentage of Phobos should be
   porous?\n Please enter a value between 0 and 1 >"))
5 percentage_icy = float(input("What percentage of Phobos should be
   icy? Please enter a value between 0 and 1 >"))
6
7 porous_cell_n = int(mesh.number_of_cells*percentage_porous)
8 icy_cell_n = int(mesh.number_of_cells*percentage_icy)
9 rocky_cells_n = mesh.number_of_cells - porous_cell_n - icy_cell_n
10
11
12 rho[2] = mpmath.mpf((mass - porous_cell_n*v*rho[0] -
   icy_cell_n*v*rho[1]) / (rocky_cells_n*v))

```

Listing 10: Implementation of the equation 11 in Python

After determining the percentages for the entire Phobos, the density value for the rocky part of Phobos is calculated. This allows us to move on to the next stage of the calculation which is the regional density allocation. In our plots, the three density types are visually distinguished: rocky cells are colored black, icy cells blue, and porous cells are white. However, when a particular region is selected, it is removed from the original mesh. To retain the original cell indices, we use the `cell_data` attribute, which records the position of each extracted cube in the original mesh. This allows us to assign the density values accurately back in the context of the original mesh geometry. The rest of the body is extracted with the function `extract_cells`. These procedures

are shown in 11.

```
1 selected_ids1 = extracted1.cell_data["vtkOriginalCellIds"]
2 selected_ids2 = extracted2.cell_data["vtkOriginalCellIds"]
3 selected_ids = extracted.cell_data["vtkOriginalCellIds"]
4 selected_ids3 = extracted3.cell_data["vtkOriginalCellIds"]
5
6 all_ids = set(range(mesh.n_cells))
7 remaining_ids = np.array(list(all_ids -
8     set(selected_ids)-set(selected_ids1)-set(selected_ids2)-set(selected_ids3)))
9
10 entire_rho = {}
11 real_coeff = {}
12 colors = np.array([[1, 1, 1],[0, 0, 1], [0, 0, 0] ]) # white blue
13     black
14 cell_colors = np.zeros((mesh.n_cells, 3))
```

Listing 11: Region Selection

Once the original IDs for each region have been obtained, the percentages of the different density types specific to each region can be determined.

```
1 # Stickney region!
2 selected_percentage_porous = float(input("What percentage of the
3     selected region should be porous?\n Please enter a value between
4     0 and 1 >"))
5 selected_percentage_icy = float(input("What percentage of the
6     selected region should be icy? Please enter a value between 0 and
7     1 >"))
8 selected_porous_cell_n =
9     int(extracted.number_of_cells*selected_percentage_porous)
10 selected_icy_cell_n =
11     int(extracted.number_of_cells*selected_percentage_icy)
12 selected_rocky_cells_n = extracted.number_of_cells -
13     selected_porous_cell_n - selected_icy_cell_n
```

Listing 12: Regional Density Allocation

Upon selecting the density percentages for the region, they are randomly assigned to the cells within the region.

```

1 selected_entire_rho = {}
2 indices = list(range(extracted.number_of_cells))
3 np.random.shuffle(indices)
4
5 for i in range(selected_porous_cell_n):
6     selected_entire_rho[indices[i]] = rho[0]
7
8 for i in range(selected_porous_cell_n, selected_porous_cell_n +
9     selected_icy_cell_n):
10    selected_entire_rho[indices[i]] = rho[1]
11
12 for i in range(selected_porous_cell_n + selected_icy_cell_n,
13     extracted.number_of_cells):
14    selected_entire_rho[indices[i]] = rho[2]

```

Listing 13: Random Density Assignment for a particular region

As the final step, the density values and their associated color data are assigned back to the original mesh.

```

1 if 'vtkOriginalCellIds' in extracted.cell_data:
2     original_ids = extracted.cell_data['vtkOriginalCellIds']
3     # Now you can iterate over the selected region cells and know which
4     cells they correspond to in the original mesh.
5     for i, orig_id in enumerate(original_ids):
6         if selected_entire_rho[i] == rho[0]:
7             cell_colors[orig_id] = colors[0]
8             entire_rho[orig_id] = rho[0]
9         elif selected_entire_rho[i] == rho[1]:
10            cell_colors[orig_id] = colors[1]
11            entire_rho[orig_id] = rho[1]
12        elif selected_entire_rho[i] == rho[2]:
13            cell_colors[orig_id] = colors[2]
14            entire_rho[orig_id] = rho[2]
15        else:
16            print("Fail!!!")

```

Listing 14: Density Allocation in the original shape

The same methodology was applied to the other regions in the mesh. At the end of

this process, the `entire_rho` dictionary contains the density values of all the cells in the original mesh based on earlier regional allocations. One should be careful when assigning percentages to a particular region as discrepancies between these and the overall Phobos density percentage may cause an error.

3.4.3 Center of Mass (CoM) calculation

In the equation 1, the first order Stokes' coefficients can be taken as 0 assuming the [Center of Figure \(CoF\)](#) coincides with the [Center of Mass \(CoM\)](#). However, due to varying density distributions within Phobos, the [Center of Mass \(CoM\)](#) might shift. To calculate the position of center of mass, the following method was applied.

```

1 x_com, y_com, z_com = mpmath.mpf("0"), mpmath.mpf("0"), mpmath.mpf("0")
2 iter = mesh.n_cells
3 v = mpmath.mpf(density**3)
4
5 for i in range(iter):
6     if i%10000==0:
7         print(100*i/iter)
8
9     mass_cube = entire_rho[i]*v
10    check_mass += mass_cube
11    cell_mesh = mesh.get_cell(i)
12    x, y, z =
        mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[0]), mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[1]), mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[2])
13
14    x_com += mass_cube*x
15    y_com += mass_cube*y
16    z_com += mass_cube*z
17
18 x_com = x_com/mass
19 y_com = y_com/mass
20 z_com = z_com/mass
21 com = [x_com, y_com, z_com]
```

Listing 15: Calculating the [Center of Mass \(CoM\)](#)

However, since the first-order coefficient inherently reflects the position of [Center of Mass \(CoM\)](#), this computation might be omitted.

3.5 Calculation of the Stokes' Coefficients of the Entire Body

Upon getting the [Center of Mass \(CoM\)](#) of the mesh, the corresponding Stokes' coefficients can be calculated for each cell in the mesh, as discussed in Section 3.3. The coefficient dictionary has a tuple as the key that indicates the i^{th} cubes, the degree and the order. The corresponding value holds the Stokes' coefficients values for each cube.

```

1 coeff = {}
2 for i in range(mesh.n_cells):
3     cell_mesh = mesh.get_cell(i)
4     x,y,z =
5         (mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[0]), mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[1]),
6         mpmath.mpmathify(cell_mesh.center[2]))
7     z = z-com[2]
8     y = y-com[1]
9     x = x-com[0]
10    r = mpmath.sqrt((x)**2+(y)**2+(z)**2)
11    for l in range(0,degree+1):
12        if l == 0:
13            coeff[(i,0,0)] =
14                [mpmath.mpmathify("1"), mpmath.mpmathify("0")]
15        elif l == 1:
16            coeff[(i,1,1)] = [x/(reference_radius*mpmath.sqrt("3"))
17                , y/(reference_radius*mpmath.sqrt("3"))]
18            coeff[(i,1,1-1)] = [ (
19                (z/reference_radius)*(2*l-1)/(mpmath.sqrt((2*l+1)))
20                *coeff[(i,1-1,1-1)][0]) ,
21                ((z/reference_radius)*(2*l-1)/(mpmath.sqrt((2*l+1)))
22                *coeff[(i,1-1,1-1)][1])]
23        for m in range(l+1,degree+1):
24            coeff[(i,m,l-1)] = [
25                (2*m-1)*(z/reference_radius)*mpmath.sqrt(
26                (2*m-1)/ (
27                (2*m+1)*(m+1-1)*(m-1+1)))*coeff[(i,m-1,l-1)][0] -
28                mpmath.sqrt( (2*m-3)*(m+1-2)*(m-1)/ (
29                (2*m+1)*(m+1-1)*(m-1+1) ) ) *
30                (r/reference_radius)**2 * coeff[(i,m-2,l-1)][0]

```

```

23         ,      (2*m-1) * (z/reference_radius) *mpmath.sqrt (
24         (2*m-1) / (
25         (2*m+1) * (m+1-1) * (m-1+1))) *coeff[ (i,m-1,l-1) ] [1] -
26         mpmath.sqrt ( (2*m-3) * (m+1-2) * (m-1) / (
27         (2*m+1) * (m+1-1) * (m-1+1) ) ) *
28         (r/reference_radius)**2 * coeff[ (i,m-2,l-1) ] [1]
29         ]
23
24     else:
25         coeff[ (i,l,l) ] = [ (2*l-1) / (mpmath.sqrt (2*l*(2*l+1))) *
26         ( x/reference_radius) *
27         coeff[ (i,l-1,l-1) ] [0] -
28         (y/reference_radius) *coeff[ (i,l-1,l-1) ] [1] ) ,
29         (2*l-1) / (mpmath.sqrt (2*l*(2*l+1))) * (
30         (y/reference_radius) *coeff[ (i,l-1,l-1) ] [0]
31         + (x/reference_radius) *coeff[ (i,l-1,l-1) ] [1] ) ]
32         coeff[ (i,l,l-1) ] = [
33         (z/reference_radius) * (2*l-1) / (mpmath.sqrt ((2*l+1)))
34         *coeff[ (i,l-1,l-1) ] [0]
35         , (z/reference_radius) * (2*l-1) / (mpmath.sqrt ((2*l+1)))
36         *coeff[ (i,l-1,l-1) ] [1]]
37
38     for m in range (l+1, degree+1) :
39         coeff[ (i,m,l-1) ] = [
40         (2*m-1) * (z/reference_radius) *mpmath.sqrt (
41         (2*m-1) /
42         ( (2*m+1) * (m+1-1) * (m-1+1))) *coeff[ (i,m-1,l-1) ] [0] -
43         mpmath.sqrt ( (2*m-3) * (m+1-2) * (m-1) / (
44         (2*m+1) * (m+1-1) * (m-1+1) ) )
45         * (r/reference_radius)**2 * coeff[ (i,m-2,l-1) ] [0]
46         ,
47         (2*m-1) * (z/reference_radius) *mpmath.sqrt (
48         (2*m-1) / ( (2*m+1) * (m+1-1) * (m-1+1)))
49         *coeff[ (i,m-1,l-1) ] [1] - mpmath.sqrt (
50         (2*m-3) * (m+1-2) * (m-1) /
51         ( (2*m+1) * (m+1-1) * (m-1+1) ) ) *
52         (r/reference_radius)**2 * coeff[ (i,m-2,l-1) ] [1]
53         ]

```



```
12 RECOEF    4  3  -1.05361912686693e-03  1.22979603948598e-03
13 RECOEF    4  4  -5.20740147957736e-04  9.10609877104149e-04
14 END
```

Listing 19: Produced .cof file for Phobos

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Spherical Homogeneous Body Example

In this section, to validate our Python implementation, we calculate the gravitational field of a voxelized spherical body. The resulting gravitational field is expected to closely approximate that of a point mass, with discrepancies diminishing as the cell size decreases. For this analysis, we consider a sphere with a radius of 13.9 km. The cell sizes will be selected to demonstrate the importance of the cell size (200 m and 500 m). The sphere is assigned the mass of Phobos. In a point mass approximation, the magnitude of the gravitational potential at a distance of 14 km is given by:

$$U = \frac{GM}{r} = \frac{0.70765 \times 10^6}{14000} = 50.55 \text{m}^2/\text{s}^2$$

Looking at Figure 19,21, as the cell size got smaller, the computed gravitational potential increasingly converges toward the point-mass approximation. Additionally, this confirms the validity of our implementation done with Python.

Figure 18: Sphere with a radius of 13.9 km (500m cubes)

Figure 19: Gravitational Field of a Vox-elized Sphere at a distance of 14 km (500m cubes)

Figure 20: Sphere with a radius of 13.9 km (200m cubes)

Figure 21: Gravitational Field of a Vox-elized Sphere at a distance of 14 km (200m cubes)

Another important issue to consider is understanding how much the gravitational potential of the voxelized sphere deviates from the analytical solution. By looking at the differences, we can have a basic idea about the error introduced by the discretization process.

Figure 22: Comparison of gravitational potential maps: the analytical solution versus the numerical solution

4.2 Homogeneous Case - Willner et al. (2014)

In the study by Le Maistre et al. (2019) [15], Stokes' coefficients for a voxelized model of Phobos (500 m) were computed up to the 10th order and presented in tabular form. To validate our methodology, we reproduced the gravitational potential map as described by that study and compared it to the one produced here. Figure 23 shows a direct comparison between the gravitational potential map generated in our work and that reported by Le Maistre et al. (2019). The largest observed deviation, approximately 1%, suggests that the voxelization tool used in Le Maistre et al. (2019) differs from the one used here. Therefore, any differences in the accuracy of the voxelization methods

should be considered when interpreting the results. Despite this discrepancy, the overall agreement between the two maps confirms the validity of our approach.

Figure 23: Comparison of 10x10 gravitational maps

4.3 Homogenous Case - Ernst et al. (2023)

As done in Section 4.2, using the shape model of Ernst et al. (2023), the two gravitational potential maps of a homogeneous Phobos were compared. As illustrated in Figure 24, the maximum deviation between the maps is approximately 1.2%.

Figure 24: Comparison of 10x10 gravitational maps

4.4 Realistic Heterogeneous Mass Distribution Modeling

In pursuit of a realistic heterogeneous mass distribution model, the studies reviewed in Section 2 were analyzed. The second-order Stokes' coefficients derived from flyby data [2] indicate a higher density along the equatorial plane, while the analysis by Le Maistre et al. (2019) [15] suggests that the material beneath the Stickney crater is compressed. Furthermore, Guo et al. (2021) propose the existence of a porous core in Phobos. Drawing on conclusions from these findings, the present study divides Phobos into five distinct regions, as detailed in Section 3.4.1. Although alternative configurations for the interior are possible, the analysis was performed using the model outlined in Section 3.4.1 for simplicity. By trying different density configurations for each region,

the density distributions given in Section 4.5 and Section 4.6 matched the coefficients calculated by Yang et al. (2019) [2] with deviations around 1%. The regions selected in Phobos are shown in Section 3.4.1.

4.5 Realistic Heterogeneous Mass Distribution - Willner et al. (2014)

Table 1: Density Percentages for Each Region

Region	Number of Cells	Rocky (%)	Icy (%)	Porous (%)
Stickney	6575	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Core	7657	13.6%	0.0%	86.4%
Equator Edges	17312	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Core Edges	3226	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Rest of the Body	15882	20.85%	21.94%	57.22%
Whole Mesh	50652	62.1%	6.9%	31.0%

Table 2: Comparison of Gravitational Coefficients

Coefficient	Normalized (Yang et al., 2019)	Computed	Relative Error (%)
\bar{C}_{20}	-0.0616260	-0.0614081	0.35%
\bar{C}_{22}	0.0257166	0.0257594	0.16%

Distribution of mass inside Phobos

Figure 25: Heterogeneous density distribution of Phobos for the Willner et al. (2014) shape model. 31.0% porous (white) , 6.9% icy (lightblue), and 62.1% rocky material (black).

4.6 Realistic Heterogeneous Mass Distribution - Ernst et al. (2023)

Table 3: Density Percentages for Each Region

Region	Number of Cells	Rocky (%)	Icy (%)	Porous (%)
Stickney	6740	100%	0%	0%
Core	7657	13.6%	0%	86.4%
Equator Edges	17103	100%	0%	0%
Core Edges	3197	100%	0%	0%
Rest of the Body	15669	20.46%	22.11%	57.42%
Whole Mesh	50366	62.1%	6.9%	31.0%

Table 4: Comparison of Gravitational Coefficients

Coefficient	Normalized (Yang et al., 2019)	Computed	Relative Error (%)
\bar{C}_{20}	-0.0616260	-0.0611742	0.73%
\bar{C}_{22}	0.0257166	0.0250226	2.69%

Distribution of mass inside Phobos

Figure 26: Heterogeneous density distribution of Phobos for the Ernst et al. (2023) shape model. 31.0% porous (white) , 6.9% icy (lightblue), and 62.1% rocky material (black).

4.7 Uncertainties in the gravitational field

Although the overall density percentages are identical for both shape models, the differences in their geometries, as discussed in Section 3.2.3, result in slightly different gravitational fields. Assuming that the true shape of Phobos lies between these two models, and taking the internal density distribution as the ground truth, our objective is to compare the gravitational fields produced by each shape model and calculate the mean difference due to the shape discrepancies [26].

Figure 27: Mean difference between the two gravitational maps in Section 4.6 and 4.5

Figure 27 illustrates that the mean difference is around $\pm 10^{-7} \text{km}^2/\text{s}^2$ which corresponds to $> 1\%$ difference.

4.8 Perturbed Phobos Environment

This section is devoted to the significance of the difference between the gravitational field of Phobos and the solar radiation pressure exerted on a solar sail about Phobos. The average of the gravitational fields created in Section 4.6 and 4.5 will be considered. Thus, the field was modeled up to degree 4, and the largest deviation from the point-mass approximation was considered. Then, these two perturbations were compared in magnitude. It is important to note that the calculations were based on several assump-

tions such as a circular orbit for Phobos, and constant solar sail pressure throughout the orbit with the sail being perpendicular to the incoming photons.

Table 5: Parameters of the solar sail and related constants

Parameter	Value
A_{sail}	900 m ²
m_{sail}	40 kg
η	0.8
W_{Mars}	588.72 $\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2}$
c	$2.99792458 \times 10^8 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{solar}} = \frac{(1 + \eta) W_{\text{Mars}} A_{\text{sail}}}{c} \hat{\mathbf{u}}$$

Figure 28 illustrates the difference between the second-order gravitational terms and the solar radiation pressure (using the solar parameter defined in Table 5 as measured from the **Center of Mass (CoM)** of Phobos. From this figure, we can see that at around 18 km above the surface, the second-order gravitational effects start to become significant. For future solar sail missions with plans to hover over Phobos, these effects could become even more crucial.

Conversely, in scenarios involving multiple flybys, Phobos' gravitational field acts as an important perturbation that must be accounted for in trajectory planning. Lastly, Figure 29 compares the force estimations obtained using a point-mass (homogeneous) approximation with those derived from a model that incorporates Phobos' non-uniform (non-homogeneous) gravitational field.

Figure 28: Comparison of forces acting on a 40 kg solar sail near Phobos, showing regions where non-spherical gravitational effects ($\ell \geq 2$ terms) exceed solar radiation pressure.

Figure 29: Comparison of gravitational force on a 40-kg solar sail calculated using the point-mass (homogeneous) model versus a non-homogeneous model that accounts for the maximum force exerted by Phobos' complex gravitational field.

5 Conclusions

By implementing Le Maistre et al. (2019) [15], our Python code reproduced the homogeneous gravitational field and the gravitational potential of a sphere. The discretized sphere is not perfectly round like real planets, so to closely approximate a point-mass we would need extremely small, computationally expensive cells. Despite this, our relative error stayed below 1%. For the heterogeneous model, our calculated coefficients closely match those of Yang et al. (2019) [2]. While librations and moments of inertia were not included due to time constraints, our modeling was based on methodologies from previous studies that consider these parameters. Future studies could include these parameters for more accurate calculations.

Comparing solar radiation pressure to Phobos's higher-order gravity terms shows that at about 18 km from the surface, these two forces are comparable. This implies that for a solar sail mission near Phobos, non-spherical gravity of Phobos cannot be neglected. Accurate trajectory design will need to account for higher-order terms.

Python, although versatile, is slower than other languages. Still, Python packages like Cython and Numba could be used to speed up computation. For future studies, these should be explored. Additionally, using [SymPy](#) to take the gradient became slower with higher-order terms. Numerical methods to compute the potential or gradient could enable faster computation.

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A Gravitational Acceleration Calculation

$$U(r, \lambda, \phi) = -\frac{GM}{r} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^{\ell} \sum_{m=0}^{\ell} \left[C_{\ell m} \cos(m\lambda) + S_{\ell m} \sin(m\lambda) \right] P_{\ell m}(\sin \phi),$$

This equation could be rewritten as;

$$\begin{aligned} U(r, \lambda, \phi) = & -\frac{GM}{r} \\ & - \frac{GM}{r} \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^{\ell} C_{\ell,0} P_{\ell,0}(\sin \phi) \\ & - \frac{GM}{r} \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^{\ell} \sum_{m=1}^{\ell} \left[C_{\ell m} \cos(m\lambda) + S_{\ell m} \sin(m\lambda) \right] P_{\ell m}(\sin \phi) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The acceleration is the gradient of the scalar potential. Assuming a perfect spherical body, one that has a homogeneous mass distribution as discussed in the Section 4.1, the Stokes' coefficients in the equation 12 will be 0. This leaves the first part of the term.

$$U(r, \lambda, \phi) = -\frac{GM}{r}$$

Taking the gradient of this function yields:

$$\mathbf{a} = -\vec{\nabla}U(r, \lambda, \phi) = -\frac{\partial(-\frac{GM}{r})}{\partial r} \hat{u}_r$$

$$\mathbf{a} = -\frac{GM}{r^2} \hat{u}_r$$

However, in reality the gravitational potential deviates from the point-mass approximation due to the non-homogeneous distribution of mass, resulting in non-zero Stokes coefficients. This phenomenon is visualized in the Figure 30.

Figure 30: Deviation of the magnitude of acceleration from the point-mass approximation. The acceleration magnitude is depicted as a radial vector from the center.

B Numpy

NumPy is a foundational package for scientific computing in Python. It provides support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a wide collection of mathematical functions to operate on them efficiently. **NumPy** is written in C and optimized for performance, making it especially suitable for numerical simulations and data processing tasks. For further details, we refer the reader to **NumPy**'s own documentation: <https://numpy.org/doc/stable/index.html>

In this project, **NumPy** was used extensively to handle and create numerical arrays. We will try to give a few examples about the functions used within our project. The package was consistently imported as;

```
1 import numpy as np
```

linspace

The function `numpy.linspace(start, stop, num)` makes a list of numbers that are evenly spaced between two values. You tell it where to start, where to stop, and how many numbers you want in between.

In this project, we used `linspace` to make rows and columns for our 2D grid.

```
1 import numpy as np
2 x = np.linspace(0, 1, 5)
```

This creates the list: `[0. , 0.25, 0.5 , 0.75, 1.]`

meshgrid

The function `numpy.meshgrid` takes two 1D lists and turns them into 2D grids. These grids show every possible pair of points from the two lists. This is useful when you want to check something at every point in a 2D space.

```
1 import numpy as np
2
3 x = np.linspace(1, 3, 3) # [1.0, 2.0, 3.0]
4 y = np.linspace(10, 30, 3) # [10.0, 20.0, 30.0]
5 X, Y = np.meshgrid(x, y)
```

This makes two 2D matrices:

X:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1.0 & 2.0 & 3.0 \\ 1.0 & 2.0 & 3.0 \\ 1.0 & 2.0 & 3.0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Y:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 10.0 & 10.0 & 10.0 \\ 20.0 & 20.0 & 20.0 \\ 30.0 & 30.0 & 30.0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Each point on the 2D grid is formed by combining values from `X[i, j]` and `Y[i, j]`, resulting in:

$$\begin{bmatrix} (1.0, 10.0) & (2.0, 10.0) & (3.0, 10.0) \\ (1.0, 20.0) & (2.0, 20.0) & (3.0, 20.0) \\ (1.0, 30.0) & (2.0, 30.0) & (3.0, 30.0) \end{bmatrix}$$

np.array(..., dtype=float)

The function `np.array(..., dtype=float)` converts a Python sequence (like a list) into a NumPy array of floating-point numbers. Specifying `dtype=float` ensures every element becomes a float (e.g., `1.0` instead of `1`).

```
1 import numpy as np
```

```

2
3 # Example list of integers
4 int_list = [1, 2, 3]
5
6 # Convert to a NumPy array of floats
7 float_array = np.array(int_list, dtype=float)
8 print(float_array)
9 # Output: [1. 2. 3.]

```

ravel()

The method `ravel()` flattens a multi-dimensional NumPy array into a one-dimensional array.

```

1 import numpy as np
2
3 # Create a 2x2 array
4 grid = np.array([[0, 1],
5                  [2, 3]])
6
7 # Flatten it into a 1D array
8 flat_grid = grid.ravel()
9 print(flat_grid)
10 # Output: [0 1 2 3]

```

np.column_stack(...)

The function `np.column_stack((a, b, c, ...))` takes several one-dimensional arrays of the same length and stacks them column-by-column to form a two-dimensional array. Each input array becomes one column in the output.

```

1 import numpy as np
2
3 # Example 1: Stack two 1D arrays into a 2x2 array
4 a = np.array([10, 20])
5 b = np.array([30, 40])
6
7 points_2d = np.column_stack((a, b))

```

```

8 print(points_2d)
9 # Output:
10 # array([[10, 30],
11 #        [20, 40]])
12
13 # Example 2: Use ravel() on three 2x2 grids and then column_stack
14 xg = np.array([[0, 1],
15               [0, 1]])
16 yg = np.array([[5, 5],
17               [6, 6]])
18 zg = np.array([[100, 200],
19               [300, 400]])
20
21 x_flat = xg.ravel() # [0, 1, 0, 1]
22 y_flat = yg.ravel() # [5, 5, 6, 6]
23 z_flat = zg.ravel() # [100,200,300,400]
24
25 points_3d = np.column_stack((x_flat, y_flat, z_flat))
26 print(points_3d)
27 # Output:
28 # array([[ 0,  5, 100],
29 #        [ 1,  5, 200],
30 #        [ 0,  6, 300],
31 #        [ 1,  6, 400]])

```

np.random.shuffle

The code below creates a list of numbers and then shuffles them in a random order. This was used to randomly assign density values with regions.

```
1 import numpy as np
2
3 numbers = list(range(10))
4 print("Before shuffle:", numbers)
5
6 np.random.shuffle(numbers)
7 print("After shuffle:", numbers)
8
9 # Possible output:
10 # Before shuffle: [0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]
11 # After shuffle: [3, 7, 0, 8, 1, 9, 6, 5, 4, 2]
```

np.deg2rad and np.rad2deg

np.deg2rad and np.rad2deg are convenience functions that convert angles between degrees and radians. Many scientific functions (e.g., trigonometric functions) expect angles in radians, so these functions help switch back and forth.

$$1 \text{ degree} = \frac{\pi}{180} \text{ radians.}$$

```
1 import numpy as np
2
3 # Example: single value
4 angle_deg = 180
5 angle_rad = np.deg2rad(angle_deg)
6 print(angle_rad)
7 # Output: 3.141592653589793 (which is pi)
8
9 # Example: array of degrees
10 angles_deg = np.array([0, 30, 45, 90])
11 angles_rad = np.deg2rad(angles_deg)
12 print(angles_rad)
13 # Output: [0.          0.52359878  0.78539816  1.57079633]
```

C Sympy

Sympy is a Python library for symbolic mathematics. Unlike **NumPy**, which works with numbers, **Sympy** works with algebraic symbols. It can be used to solve equations, simplify expressions, take derivatives, and even integrate functions, all symbolically, just like you would on paper. For further details, we refer the reader to Sympy's own documentation: <https://docs.sympy.org/latest/index.html>

In this project, **Sympy** was useful for defining gravitational formulas and performing exact calculations before turning them into numerical code in **NumPy**. We will try to give a few examples about the functions used within our project. The package was consistently imported as;

```
1 import sympy as sp
```

symbols

The function `symbols` is used to define variables.

```
1 import sympy as sp
2
3 x, y = sp.symbols('x y')
```

Now `x` and `y` act like algebraic variables.

simplify

The function `simplify` tries to make a mathematical expression simpler. It applies different algebraic rules to reduce the expression to its most compact or readable form.

```
1 expr = (x**2 - 1)/(x - 1)
2 simplified_expr = sp.simplify(expr)
```

This returns:

$$x + 1$$

diff

The function `diff` computes the derivative of a symbolic expression. It can handle both ordinary and partial derivatives depending on how it is used.

```
1 f = x**2 + 3*x + 1 + y
2 dfdx = sp.diff(f, x)
```

The result is:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x}(x^2 + 3x + 1 + y) = 2x + 3$$

lambdify

The function `lambdify` converts symbolic expressions into numerical functions that can be used with regular Python or [NumPy](#) values. To specify the type of backend for numerical operations, a third argument can be provided as a string (e.g., "numpy"). If omitted, it defaults to standard Python math. Using [NumPy](#) is often preferred for performance, since [NumPy](#) functions are implemented in C and run faster.

```
1 f = x**2 + 3*x + 1 + y
2 f_func = sp.lambdify((x, y), f, "numpy")
3 f_func(2, 1) # returns 12
```

This means the symbolic function $f = x^2 + 3x + 1 + y$ can now be used just like any normal Python function. For example:

$$f(2, 1) = 2^2 + 3 \cdot 2 + 1 + 1 = 12$$

This becomes especially useful when plotting such functions using [Matplotlib](#) or when performing large-scale numerical evaluations.

subs

The `subs` method substitutes a value into a symbolic expression.

```
1 f.subs(x, 2).subs(y, 1)
```

This also returns:

12

evalf

The function `evalf()` stands for "evaluate to floating point." It turns a symbolic (exact) expression into a decimal (approximate) number. This is useful when you want a numerical answer instead of keeping everything in terms of symbols like π or e .

```
1 expr = sp.pi + sp.sqrt(2)
2 expr.evalf(500)
```

Here, `sp.pi + sp.sqrt(2)` is an exact symbolic expression. By calling `evalf(500)`, we get its approximate decimal value up to 500 decimal places.

cancel

The function `cancel()` simplifies rational expressions by canceling common factors in the numerator and denominator. It is useful for cleaning up fractions symbolically.

```
1 expr = (x**2 - 1)/(x - 1)
2 simplified = sp.cancel(expr)
```

The original expression is:

$$\frac{x^2 - 1}{x - 1}$$

Since $x^2 - 1$ factors as $(x - 1)(x + 1)$, the common $(x - 1)$ term cancels out, giving:

$$\frac{x^2 - 1}{x - 1} = x + 1$$

So, `cancel()` returns the simplified result:

$$x + 1$$

factorial

The function `factorial()` returns the product of all positive integers up to a given number, commonly written as $n!$. It can also handle non-integer values and evaluate them using the Gamma function.

```
1 sp.factorial(5)
```

This returns:

$$5! = 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 = 120$$

assoc_legendre

The function `assoc_legendre(n, m, x)` gives the associated Legendre function $P_n^m(x)$.

```
1 sp.assoc_legendre(2, 1, x)
```

This returns:

$$P_2^1(x) = -3x\sqrt{1-x^2}$$

- n - the degree.
- m - the order.
- x - the variable.

D Matplotlib

[Matplotlib](https://matplotlib.org/stable/contents.html) is a popular Python library used for creating graphs and plots. It helps visualize data in many formats, such as line plots, scatter plots, histograms, and more. The most common module is `pyplot`, which provides a simple interface similar to MATLAB's plotting functions. For more details, visit the official documentation: <https://matplotlib.org/stable/contents.html>. The `matplotlib.pyplot` was consistently imported as;

```
1 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

Figure and subplot

In [Matplotlib](#), a `Figure` is the overall window or page that holds one or more plots (called axes). You can think of it as the canvas for your drawings.

A subplot (or axis) is a specific area inside the figure where a plot is drawn. You can have multiple subplots arranged in rows and columns inside one figure.

In this project, the following code was used consistently to create plots:

```
1 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
2
3 # Create a new figure (canvas)
4 fig = plt.figure()
5
6 # Add a subplot to the figure: 1 row, 1 column, first subplot
7 ax = plt.subplot(1, 1, 1)
```

Here, `plt.subplot(1, 1, 1)` means the figure will have 1 row and 1 column of subplots (just one plot), and 1 specifies the first (and only) subplot.

If you want to create multiple plots in the same figure, you can change these numbers. For example:

```
1 fig = plt.figure()
2
3 # Create a figure with 2 rows and 2 columns of subplots
4 ax1 = plt.subplot(2, 2, 1) # first subplot
5 ax2 = plt.subplot(2, 2, 2) # second subplot
6 ax3 = plt.subplot(2, 2, 3) # third subplot
7 ax4 = plt.subplot(2, 2, 4) # fourth subplot
```

This would create a 2-by-2 grid of plots inside the same figure.

ax.plot

The method `ax.plot(x_values, y_values)` draws a line on the axes `ax`. You can optionally add a `label` for the legend and specify a `color`. All the options can

be found in the [Matplotlib](#) official documentation.

```
1 # Simple line from (0,0) to (2,4)
2 ax.plot([0, 1, 2], [0, 1, 4])
```

ax.tick_params

`ax.tick_params(axis=..., which=..., labelsize=..., length=..., width=...)` customizes tick marks and tick labels on the specified axis.

```
1 ax.tick_params(axis='both',
2               which='major',
3               labelsize=17,
4               length=8,
5               width=1.5)
```

- `axis='both'` applies settings to both the x and y axes.
- `which='major'` targets major ticks only (ignores minor ticks).
- `labelsize=17` sets the font size of tick labels.
- `length=8` controls the length of the tick marks.
- `width=1.5` controls the line width (thickness) of tick marks.

ax.xaxis.set_major_locator and ticker.MaxNLocator

The method `ax.xaxis.set_major_locator(ticker.MaxNLocator(nbins=N))` controls how many ticks appear on the x-axis. `MaxNLocator` chooses up to `nbins` “nice” tick locations.

```
1 import matplotlib.ticker as ticker
2
3 ax.xaxis.set_major_locator(ticker.MaxNLocator(nbins=3))
4 ax.yaxis.set_major_locator(ticker.MaxNLocator(nbins=3))
```

- `nbins=3` tells [Matplotlib](#) to use at most 3 major ticks on each axis.
- `ticker.MaxNLocator` finds evenly spaced, readable tick values for the axis.

ax.grid

The method `ax.grid(linestyle="--")` draws grid lines on the plot, making it easier to read values.

```
1 ax.grid(linestyle="--")
```

ax.annotate

The method `ax.annotate(text, xy=(x, y), xytext=(x_text, y_text), arrowprops=dict(...), fontsize=...)` places a text annotation at `xytext` and draws an arrow pointing to `xy`. This highlights a specific point on the plot.

```
1 fig = plt.figure()
2 ax = plt.subplot(1,1,1)
3 x = [1, 2, 3]
4 y = [2, 4, 1]
5
6 ax.plot(x, y)
7
8 # Annotate the second point
9 ax.annotate("Peak",
10             xy=(2, 4),
11             xytext=(2.5, 4.5),
12             arrowprops=dict(arrowstyle="->"))
13 plt.show()
```

ax.set_xlabel and ax.set_ylabel

These methods label the x-axis and y-axis of the subplot, respectively.

```
1 ax.set_xlabel("Distance from the center of mass of Phobos (km)",
2             fontsize=18)
3 ax.set_ylabel("Force (N)", fontsize=18)
```

ax.legend

The method `ax.legend(fontsize=...)` displays a legend on the axes, showing line labels given in `ax.plot`. `fontsize=14` sets the text size inside the legend box.

```
1 ax.legend(fontsize=14)
```

inset_axes

To create an inset (a smaller subplot inside a larger plot), the function `inset_axes(parent_ax, width="x%", height="y%", loc="location")` from `mpl_toolkits.axes_grid1.inset_locator` is used. It places a new axes inside the main axes. All the functions for `ax` can be used to edit `ax_inset`.

```
1 from mpl_toolkits.axes_grid1.inset_locator import inset_axes
2 ax_inset = inset_axes(ax,
3                       width="50%",    # 50% of parent axes width
4                       height="50%",   # 50% of parent axes height
5                       loc="center right")
```

plt.savefig and plt.show

After creating and customizing a figure, you can save it to a file and/or display it on the screen:

```
1 plt.savefig("filename.pdf")
2 plt.show()
```

contourf and colorbar

The method `ax.contourf(X, Y, Z, levels=..., cmap=...)` creates a filled contour plot, showing regions of constant value in the array `Z`. Each region is colored according to a colormap. To add a color scale next to the plot, use `plt.colorbar(label=...)`.

```
1 x = np.linspace(-2, 2, 100)
2 y = np.linspace(-2, 2, 100)
3 X, Y = np.meshgrid(x, y)
```

```

4 Z = X**2 + Y**2 # Simple scalar field
5
6 fig = plt.figure()
7 ax = plt.subplot(1, 1, 1)
8
9
10 contour = ax.contourf(X, Y, Z, levels=50, cmap="viridis")
11 plt.colorbar(contour, label="Z")
12
13 ax.set_xlabel("X")
14 ax.set_ylabel("Y")
15 ax.set_title("Simple Contour Plot")
16 plt.show()

```

E PyVista

PyVista is a Python library that provides an easy interface for 3D visualization and mesh analysis, built on top of the Visualization Toolkit. It is particularly useful for working with complex geometries, surface meshes, and volumetric data in scientific computing and engineering applications. For more information and examples, we refer the reader to the official PyVista documentation: <https://docs.pyvista.org/>.

The package was consistently imported as:

```

1 import pyvista as pv

```

Creating a Mesh in PyVista

In **PyVista**, a mesh represents the geometry of a 3D object, typically consisting of vertices and faces. Meshes can be created from scratch or loaded from files such as stl, vtk, or obj formats.

```

1 import pyvista as pv
2 mesh = pv.Sphere(radius=1.0, theta_resolution=30, phi_resolution=30)

```

The `pv.Sphere()` function generates a spherical mesh. Other functions such as `Box()`, `Cube()`, `Cylinder()`, and `Plane()` are also available.

.read()

This method reads a mesh from a file and returns a mesh object. It supports various file formats.

```
1 # Read a mesh from a file
2 mesh = pv.read('path/to/your_mesh_file.vtk')
```

.volume

This property returns the approximate volume of a closed mesh. It calculates the space enclosed by the mesh's surface.

```
1 sphere = pv.Sphere(radius=0.1)
2
3 vol = sphere.volume
4 print("Volume:", vol)
```

.voxelize()

The method `mesh.voxelize()` converts a continuous 3D object into a grid of discrete cubic cells called voxels.

```
1 # Convert the mesh into a voxel-based representation
2 voxelized = mesh.voxelize(density=50.0)
```

Plotter()

The class `pv.Plotter()` is used to create an interactive 3D plotting window in [PyVista](#), similar to [Matplotlib](#). It acts as a canvas where you can add and render multiple meshes, control camera position, add text, show axes, and save visual outputs.

After creating a `Plotter` object, you can add 3D meshes to it using methods like `add_mesh()`, adjust the view with `camera_position`, and display the final result with `show()`.

```
1 import pyvista as pv
2
```

```
3 | plotter = pv.Plotter() # Create an empty plotting window
4 | plotter.add_mesh(my_mesh) # Add a mesh object to the scene
5 | plotter.show()
```

.clip_box(bounds, ...)

This method clips the mesh using a bounding box defined by `bounds = (x_min, x_max, y_min, y_max, z_min, z_max)`. It returns a new mesh containing only the geometry inside the box.

You can control options like:

- `invert=True` to keep everything *outside* the box.
- `crinkle=True` to preserve the original surface features.
- `progress_bar=True` to show progress during computation.

```
1 | clipped = mesh.clip_box(bounds, invert=False, crinkle=True)
```

.merge(other)

The `merge()` method combines two meshes into one. This is useful if you've clipped multiple regions or created geometry in parts and want to view them together.

```
1 | combined = mesh.merge(other_mesh)
```

.extract_surface()

This method extracts only the outer surface of a mesh, removing internal cells.

```
1 | surface_mesh = mesh.extract_surface()
```

.extract_geometry()

This method extracts only the surface geometry from a mesh, removing internal structure or metadata.

```
1 surface = mesh.extract_geometry()
```

.compute_implicit_distance()

This method calculates the implicit distance at each point of a mesh or its surface. The implicit distance measures how far each point is from a reference geometry (often another mesh). By using `inplace=True`, the method adds a new scalar array to the mesh's point data while keeping the original Cartesian coordinates.

```
1 sphere = pv.Sphere(radius=0.1)
2 plane = pv.Plane()
3 dist_with_points = sphere.compute_implicit_distance(plane,
4     inplace=True)
5 dist = sphere['implicit_distance']
```

.threshold()

This method selects parts of a mesh based on a range of scalar values. It keeps only the cells whose scalar values are within the given limits.

```
1 surface_mesh = mesh.extract_surface()
2 mesh_with_distance = mesh.compute_implicit_distance(surface_mesh)
3 # The expected value should be 0 given that they are the same shape.
4 # However, the functions allows us to select negative distance, in
5 # other words, parts of the mesh below the surface
6 negative_thresh_mesh = mesh_with_distance.threshold([-500, 0],
7     scalars="implicit_distance")
```

F Mpmath

[Mpmath](#) is a Python library for arbitrary-precision arithmetic, useful when high precision beyond standard floating-point is needed. It provides data types and functions to

work with numbers of arbitrary size and precision. For more details, visit the official documentation: <https://mpmath.org/doc/current/>.

mp.dps

The attribute `mpmath.mp.dps` sets the number of decimal places for calculations performed by **Mpmath**. Increasing `mp.dps` increases the precision of all subsequent arithmetic operations.

```
1 import mpmath
2 mpmath.mp.dps = 100 # Set precision to 100 decimal places
```

mpf

The `mpmath.mpf` type represents a high-precision floating-point number. It allows calculations with a precision specified by the user, rather than the fixed double precision of standard floats.

```
1 import mpmath
2
3 # Set precision to 50 decimal places
4 mpmath.mp.dps = 50
5 x = mpmath.mpf('1.234567890123456789')
6 print(x)
```

mpmathify

The function `mpmath.mpmathify` converts standard Python numeric types (like `int` or `float`) into `mpf` objects, enabling high-precision operations on them.

```
1 import mpmath
2 # Convert a float to mpf
3 high_prec_num = mpmath.mpmathify(3.141592653589793)
4 print(high_prec_num)
```

G Python Code for Creating a .cof File

```
1 import numpy as np
2 import sympy as sp
3
4
5 def kronecker(m):
6     if m == 0:
7         return 1
8     else:
9         return 0
10
11
12 coeff = {}
13
14 degree = 4
15
16 name = "Phobos-Willner-4x4-coeff-500.0"
17
18 with open(f"{name}.txt", "r") as g:
19     for line in g:
20         line = line.strip().split()
21         print(line)
22         n = line[0]
23         m = line[1]
24         Anm = line[2]
25         Bnm = line[3]
26
27
28         n = int(n)
29         m = int(m)
30
31         if m > degree:
32             degree = m
33         Anm = float(Anm)
34         Bnm = float(Bnm)
35         Anm = float(Anm)
36         Bnm = float(Bnm)
37
```



```

69         f.write(f"RECOEF   {n:2d} {m:2d}   {coeff[(n,
70                 m)][0]:.14e}{coeff[(n, m)][1]:.14e}\n")
71     elif coeff[(n, m)][0] < 0:
72         f.write(f"RECOEF   {n:2d} {m:2d}   {coeff[(n,
73                 m)][0]:.14e} {coeff[(n, m)][1]:.14e}\n")
74     elif coeff[(n, m)][1] < 0:
75         f.write(f"RECOEF   {n:2d} {m:2d}   {coeff[(n,
76                 m)][0]:.14e}{coeff[(n, m)][1]:.14e}\n")
77     else:
78         f.write(f"RECOEF   {n:2d} {m:2d}   {coeff[(n,
79                 m)][0]:.14e} {coeff[(n, m)][1]:.14e}\n")
80
81 f.write("END")

```

Listing 20: .cof file in Python

H The Code for Fixing the Shape model

```
1 import pyvista as pv
2 import pymeshfix
3
4 name = "phobos-willner14-400.obj"
5 grid = pv.read(name)
6 #
7 -----
8 # I fixed the errors in the mesh (Willner14) by using pymeshfix
9 # Source:
10 https://pymeshfix.pyvista.org/examples/cow.html#sphx-glr-examples-cow-py
11 #
12 -----
13 print("Attempting to fix ...")
14 grid = pymeshfix.MeshFix(grid)
15 grid.repair(joincomp=True, remove_smallest_components=False)
16 grid.repair(verbose=True)
17 grid = grid.mesh
18
19 grid.save("phobos-willner14-fixed.obj")
```

Listing 21: Fixing the .obj file in Python